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“YOU”

When I first saw you,
You wore red shirts.
Your hair sucked.
Your nails were black.
You were rugged and lost.
But with your pure heartbeats,
You colored my world with cheeriness.

Oh, how wonderful life is with you!
In your arms, I feel so secured.
Your smile triggers my “feel-good” chemicals.
Your sweet words caress me.
Your passionate love diverges myself to a wider view.

From that very moment you promised me,
You never stop showing to me the rainbow that won't fade.
You share crazy secrets and problems.
You share things I don't even like.
You act and make faces I so hate.
But under the deep roots of my being,
That style makes me feel so great.

You may age in the years to come,
You may not hear even my whispers,
You may not hug me as tightly as I want,
But that single word will always remain.
Now and forever I will carry that thing,
For you my one and only dear!